

The Effects of Affective Dimension of Face on Facial Attractiveness

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Abstract : This study examined what effective dimension affects facial attractiveness. Two orthogonal dimensions, sharp-soft and babyish-mature, were used to rate the levels of facial attractiveness in 20's women. This research also investigated the sex difference on the effect of effective dimension of face on attractiveness. The test subjects composed of 15 males and 18 females. They looked 330 photos of women in 20s. Then they rated the levels of the effective dimensions of faces with sharp-soft and babyish-mature, and the attraction with charmless-charming. The respond forms were Likert scales, the answer was scored from 1 to 9. As a result of multiple regression analysis, the subject reported the milder and younger appearance as more attractive. Both male and female subjects showed the same evaluation. This result means that two effective dimensions have the effect on estimating attractiveness.

Keywords : affective dimension of faces, facial attractiveness, sharp-soft, babyish-mature

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